

Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium with *N*-Benzoyl-*N*-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine

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A highly sensitive spectrophotometric method for determination of traces of vanadium in presence of all ions, except tungstate and molybdate, by *N*-benzoyl-*N*-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine has been proposed. The violet complex on extraction into chloroform obeys Beer's law at its maximum absorption region (530 m μ) with the optimum range from 2-8 μ g. where the %relative error is only 2.7. The complex, with the dissociation constant in the order of 10^{-6} , contains the metal and the reagent in a ratio of 1:2.

For the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium, reagents like cupferron¹, 8-quinolinol², and diphenylbenzidine³ were proposed. These reagents are fairly sensitive, but they lack in selectivity. The ions, which generally associate vanadium, interfere seriously and hence their preliminary separation by ion-exchange or electrolysis is necessary. Later investigations showed the reagents like formaldoxime⁴, salicyl⁵, benzo⁶, nicotino⁷, and isonicotino⁸ hydroxamic acids to be very useful for the purpose. But even in these cases ions of iron, copper, nickel, cobalt, manganese, aluminium, chromium, titanium, thorium, and uranium interfere.

N-Benzoyl-*N*-phenyl⁹⁻¹⁰, *N*-cinnamoyl-*N*-phenyl¹¹, *N*-2-thiophenocarbonyl-*N*-*p*-tolyl-, and *N*-2-thiophenocarbonyl-*N*-phenyl¹²-hydroxylamines are quite sensitive and effective for determination of vanadium, provided that molybdate, tungstate, titanium, and zirconium are absent.

In this communication is reported the findings of a recent study on the use of a new reagent, *N*-benzoyl-*N*-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine,

which forms in a strongly acid solution a violet complex with the vanadate ion. The intensity of the colour of the complex, on extraction with chloroform, forms the basis of a

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very sensitive and selective method for the spectrophotometric determination of a minute amount of vanadium in presence of a large excess of all common cations and anions, including borate, phosphate, fluoride, acetate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, and EDTA.

The advantage of this method is that it permits a wide limit of the common variables, such as the acidity, the volume of the aqueous phase, the temperature, and the amount of reagent used. The coloured complex is formed instantaneously in fairly strong acid solution. Other metal complexes, formed by this reagent, are decomposed at this high acidity.

The coloured complex obeys Beer's law from 0.5 $\mu\text{g.}$ to 8 $\mu\text{g.}$ with the optimum range¹³ from 2 $\mu\text{g.}$ to 8 $\mu\text{g.}$ The relative error, as calculated from Ayres' equation¹⁴, is 2.7%. The study of the composition and the dissociation constant of the complex by Job's¹⁵⁻¹⁶ and molar ratio methods¹⁷⁻¹⁸ suggests that the complex contains one vanadium atom associated with two molecules of the reagent, with the dissociation constant in the order of 10^{-8} .

The method is one of the most sensitive spectrophotometric methods so far described for the determination of vanadium. The sensitivity of its reaction, as defined by Sandell¹⁹, is 0.011 $\mu\text{g.}$ of V/cm² at 530m μ .

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent, *N*-benzoyl-*N*-*p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine, was prepared from *p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine and benzoyl chloride. *p*-Chlorophenylhydroxylamine was prepared from *p*-chloronitrobenzene by reduction in presence of ammonium chloride with zinc dust in dilute ethanol. The *p*-chlorophenylhydroxylamine separating on cooling the hot solution in ice-bath was then coupled in warm aqueous solution by benzoyl chloride in accordance with the procedure followed for *N*-benzoyl-*o*-tolylhydroxylamine²⁰. The product was extracted with liquor ammonia and the ammoniacal extract was added slowly to ice-cold sulphuric acid solution (1:5). The crystals separating were filtered, washed, and recrystallised from ethanol. The crystals of m.p. 155° were analysed. (Found : C, 63.90; H, 4.11; N, 5.82. Calc.: C, 63.3; H, 4.04; N, 5.65%).

Unicam SP600 was used for the measurement of absorbances. A standard solution of vanadium(V) was prepared from ammonium metavanadate, dissolved in dilute ammonia, and diluted to a known volume with distilled water. Its vanadium content per ml was estimated by complexometric titration²¹.

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A 0.5% solution of the reagent was prepared with chloroform which was freed beforehand from ethanol and other impurities by washing first with a few drops of H_2SO_4 and then successively with dilute ammonia and water.

Procedure.—An aliquot portion of the vanadium (v) solution was transferred to a separating funnel and to which was added 10 ml of 4-8*N*-HCl. The vanadium was then extracted into the organic layer after addition of 4 ml of the reagent solution plus 6 ml of purified chloroform and shaking for a few minutes. To be sure of the complete recovery, the aqueous layer was once again extracted with 5 ml of the purified chloroform. The combined extract was taken into a 25-ml calibrated flask and made to volume with chloroform. The optical density of this solution was measured at different wave lengths; its maximum absorption was found to be at 530 $m\mu$ (Fig. 1). The vanadium complex is soluble also in benzene, CCl_4 , xylene, and methyl isobutyl ketone; in all these solvents the region of maximum absorbance is practically the same. The solvents used must not be contaminated with ethanol or acetone as these reduce the colour intensity of the vanadium complex.

Effect of Acidity, Reagent, and Time.—Maximum colour intensity was obtained with 4 to 8*N* of HCl and the colour system maintained the intensity of colour at the room temperature for over 5 days. The reagent had no effect on the colour system and hence even a large excess of it (4 ml of 0.5%) could be used for only 4 μ g. of vanadium.

Beer's Law, Optimum Range, and Photometric Error.—The system obeys Beer's law from 0.5 μ g. to 8 μ g. at 530 $m\mu$ and the optimum range, as calculated according to Ringbom¹³, is from 2 μ g. to 8 μ g. (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1. Spectral transmittancy curve.

FIG. 2. Standard curve.

The %relative error per 1% absolute photometric error, as calculated according to Ayres' equation¹⁴, is 2.7 (Fig. 3).

Effect of Diverse Ions.—The effect of foreign ions was investigated and found that even 4 μ g. of vanadium could be determined in presence of many foreign metals. Al^{3+} (20 mg.), Ba^{2+} (20 mg.), Ca^{2+} (15 mg.), Co^{2+} (15 mg.), Cr^{3+} (20 mg.), Cu^{2+} (20 mg.), Fe^{3+} (30 mg.),

Mg²⁺ (15 mg.), Ti⁴⁺ (30 mg.), Mn²⁺ (20 mg.), Ni²⁺ (20 mg.), Th⁴⁺ (24 mg.), Sn⁴⁺ (18 mg.), UO₂²⁺ (20 mg.), Zn²⁺ (10 mg.), Zr⁴⁺ (20 mg.), Be²⁺ (20 mg.), Cd²⁺ (15 mg.), Hg²⁺ (15 mg.), Pb²⁺ (20 mg.), As³⁺ (10 mg.), As⁵⁺ (15 mg.), rare earths (20 mg.), Bi³⁺ (20 mg.), acetate (15 mg.), borate (15 mg.), citrate (10 mg.), tartrate (15 mg.), oxalate (20 mg.), phosphate (20 mg.), fluoride (30 mg.), and E.D.T.A. (20 mg.) did not interfere. In the case of Cu²⁺ and Ti⁴⁺, E.D.T.A. and sodium fluoride were used, respectively, as masking agents.

For the determination of vanadium in presence of iron, to an aliquot portion of the vanadium solution, containing 4 μ g. of vanadium, H₂SO₄(dil.) and then a drop or two of N/10-KMNO₄ solution were added until a faint pink colour developed. From this solution vanadium was extracted according to the procedure described above.

Composition of the Complex.—The composition of the violet complex was studied by Job's method of continued variation¹⁵. Absorption due to mixtures (with total volume constant) of equimolar solutions at the room temperature (28°) was measured at 530 m μ against chloroform as blank, as the reagent solution in chloroform had no absorption at this wave-length region. The peak of the curve, obtained by plotting the optical density against increasing amounts of vanadium, indicates that the violet complex contains the metal and the reagent in 1:2 ratio (Fig. 4). This composition was verified by molar ratio method, where solutions were so prepared that the vanadium (v) concentration remained constant but the ratio of the moles of the reagent to the moles of vanadium varied.

FIG. 3. Relative error from Ayres' equation.

FIG. 4. Job's method of composition.
Curve 1: Vanadium=Reagent= $1 \times 10^{-3} M$.
Curve 2: Vanadium=Reagent= $0.75 \times 10^{-3} M$.

The optical densities of chloroform-extracted solutions were measured at 530 m μ against chloroform as blank. The curve in Fig. 5 shows a break at the molar ratio of 1:2.

Molar Extinction Coefficient and Sensitivity.—The molar extinction coefficient, calculated from Beer's law curve, is 4500. The sensitivity of the reagent, as defined by Sandell, is 0.011 $\mu\text{g. of V/cm}^2$ at 530 μ .

FIG. 5. Molar-ratio method of composition.
Curve 1: Vanadium = Reagent = $1 \times 10^{-3}M$; 3 ml of V(v) used.
Curve 2: Vanadium = Reagent = $0.75 \times 10^{-3}M$; 3 ml of V(v) used.

FIG. 6. Job's method of dissociation constant.
Curve 1: Vanadium = $0.5 \times 10^{-3}M$,
Reagent = $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$.
Curve 2: Vanadium = $0.45 \times 10^{-3}M$,
Reagent = $2.25 \times 10^{-3}M$.

Dissociation Constant.—From the absorption data of the mixtures of non-equimolar solutions (Fig. 6.), the dissociation constant, K , has been calculated from Job's equation¹⁵. The results obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

V conc.	Reagent conc.	m .	n .	p .	x .	K^{28} .	K_{av} .
$0.50 \times 10^{-3}M$	$2.50 \times 10^{-3}M$	1	2	5	0.4	5×10^{-8}	3.5×10^{-8}
0.45×10^{-3}	2.25×10^{-3}	1	2	5	0.4	2×10^{-8}	

By molar ratio method⁸, the dissociation constant, K , was calculated from

$$\frac{(m \alpha c)^m (n \alpha c)^n}{c(1-\alpha)} \text{ with } \alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

The value of α is 0.28 and therefore the value of K is 9×10^{-8} .

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